

54th Conference on Manufacturing Systems 2021

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A meta-model for modular composition of tailored human digital twins in production

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Outline

Context and research gap

Many examples exist where digital copies of machines, devices, products or entire production systems are used to improve performance, make predictions and take decisions.

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Humans have been excluded, up to now, from the digital representation of the factory.

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Workers' behaviour and status is monitored and/or predicted by analysing real-time and historical data aiming to optimise processes and to make better decisions.

1. Existent literature on digital representation of human

Only a **handful of works** addressing the Human Digital Twin (or more in general human modelling in industrial contexts) can be found.

Workers have been considered, in the overall factory digital representation, mainly from a high-level perspective by creating **mere static digital models**.

2. Main entities to holistically represent human in the digital world

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3. The Human Digital Twin metamodel

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The meta-model identifies three primary descriptive elements that characterise the worker from different points of view: **workerCharacteristic**, **workerCondition**, **psychophysicalParameter**.

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The **functionalModel** describes all those computational processes that can elaborate entities and attributes, making the HDT capable of simulating, predicting, reasoning, and deciding

4. Validation in an industrial context

To start the production process, operator activates the COMPLEMANT system, logs in and connects his/her devices.

Complete video available here

Complete description of the industrial case and concept available in:

Bettoni, A. et Al. (2020). Mutualistic and adaptive human-machine collaboration based on machine learning in an injection moulding manufacturing line. Procedia CIRP, 93, 395-400.

4. Validation in an industrial context

HDT model for the experiment, have been designed and developed on the basis of the HDT meta-model.

A specific representation has been dedicated to the connections characterised by events.

Next steps

- Functional representation of the HDT to describe, in a hierarchical and modular approach, the functional composition of the HDT building blocks (e.g. data acquisition, data analysis, decision-making, etc.).
- Development of libraries to support the creation of new HDT instances in order to allow the validation in other contexts.
- Align the HDT to already existing approaches and standards (e.g. RAMI)

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Thank You!

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